

DIELECTRIC CONSTANT AND DIPOLE MOMENT OF SOME DRUGS. PART I

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The dielectric constant of santonin, barbitones, phenacetin, acetanilide and acetylsalicylic acid has been for the first time determined and the moments have been calculated by applying the new equation. The moment of *l*-ascorbic acid has been recalculated.

Dipole moment of *l*-ascorbic acid in dioxane solution has been studied by Kumler (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1940, **62**, 3292); the results have been recalculated by applying the new equation developed by Jatkar, Sathe and Iyengar (*J. Ind. Inst. Sci.*, 1946, **28A**, Part II, pp. 1-15)

TABLE I

w_2	ϵ	d	P_2	$\mu \times 10^{18}$
Solvent=dioxane. Temp.=25°. $P_H=152.8$.				
0.0000	2.21366	1.0280	—	—
0.003955	2.25919	1.02996	2079.6	3.22
0.006030	2.28458	1.03070	2126.3	3.25
0.009054	2.32136	1.03218	2342.0	3.28

The symbols used in the tables are : w_2 , wt. fraction of the solute ; d , the density of the solution ; P_2 , the polarisation of the solute ; P_e , the electronic polarisation of the solute; ϵ , the dielectric constant; μ , the dipole moment (cf. Kumler, *loc. cit.*).

The new value of moment is 3.25 as against the D. C. M. value 3.93D. Kumler has proposed the structure

with an intramolecular hydrogen bonding. It is not possible to prepare a model of this compound as there is a considerable strain in the pentacyclic unsaturated ring and hence it is not possible to explain the dipole moment.

Santonin

The chemistry of santonin was investigated by Cannizaro *et al* (cf. Clemo, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 2368) and various constitutional formulae have been suggested of which

structure (I) was proposed by Grassi-Cristaldi (cf. Gucci and Grassi-Cristaldi, *Gazzetta*, 1892, 22, 1) and structure (II) by Clemo *et al* (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 2579) after direct synthesis of *dl*-santonous acid and racemic desmotropo-santonin. No previous work has been done to study the dipole moment of santonin.

The dielectric constant of santonin was measured in benzene solution at 3 concentrations and two temperatures. The results are given below.

TABLE II

w_2	ϵ_s	d	P_2	$\mu \times 10^{18}$
Solvent=benzene. Temp.=21°.				
0.00503	2.3270	0.8934	3531	4.14
0.02002	2.6250	0.8785	5192	5.10
0.02614	2.7990	0.8823	5841	5.40
Solvent=Benzene. Temp.=42°.				
0.00503	2.2970	0.8576	3300	4.11
0.02002	2.5788	0.8617	4975	5.10
0.02614	2.7286	0.8621	5523	5.43

There is an unusually marked effect of concentration on the dipole moment. The moment of santonin in benzene solution varies with concentration, the infinite dilution value being 3.7D. This value supports structure (II). The two C=O groups are nearly at an angle of 120 degrees in (II) and 150° in (I). Calculating the components along the two polarisable groups C=O in (II), the moment along $C=O_2 = [3.0 (C-O) + 1/8 (3.0) (C=O) + 1.8 (C-O) - 1/2 \times 1.8 (C-O)] = 3.5$ and along $C=O_1 = 3.0 (C-O) - 1/8 [3.0 (C=O) + 1.8 (C-O) - 1/2 (C-O)] = 3.5$ D. The hydrocarbon groups contribute the balance of 0.2D.

Barbitone

No previous work has been reported on the dielectric constant of barbitone and phenobarbitone. In the present paper the moments of these compounds in dioxane solution have been studied.

TABLE III

w_2	ϵ	d	P_2	$\mu \times 10^{18}$
Barbitone: Solvent = dioxane. Temp. = 25°. $P_2 = 190.5$.				
0.0887	2.2622	1.0466	414.6	1.10
0.0835	2.2556	1.0468	411.6	1.10
0.0725	2.2477	1.0433	441.3	1.10
Phenobarbitone: Solvent = dioxane. Temp. = 25°. $P_2 = 228.4$.				
0.1037	2.2808	1.0557	498.4	1.20
0.0703	2.2477	1.0433	443.3	1.16

TABLE IV

Temp.	w_2	ϵ	d	P_2	$\mu \times 10^{18}$
1. Acetanilide: Solvent = benzene. $P_2 = 150$.					
22°	0.0103	2.432	0.8764	2495	3.55
44°	"	2.373	0.8592	2028	3.55
Solvent = dioxane.					
23°	0.07128	3.618	1.038	2835	3.78
40°	"	3.497	1.023	2656	3.76
2. Phenacetin: Pure (molten) liquid. $P_2 = 200$.					
Temp.		ϵ	d	P_2	
165°		24.157	1.008	4117.0	5.56
150°		25.848	1.017	4375.0	5.64
135°		27.985	1.027	4707.0	5.75
Solvent = dioxane.					
	w_2	ϵ	d	P_2	
25°	0.0180	2.681	1.0311	5373	5.30
35°	"	2.671	1.0219	5377	5.35
3. Acetylsalicylic acid: Solvent = dioxane. Temp. = 25°. $P_2 = 179.6$.					
w_2	ϵ	d	P_2		
0.0255	2.2583	1.0351	802.4		2.07
0.0673	2.473	1.044	1017.0		2.11
Solvent = dioxane. Temp. = 35°.					
0.0255	2.2470	1.027	719.8		2.00
0.0673	2.426	1.031	910.3		2.02

(The variation of moment 1.16–1.20D in the case of phenobarbitone is within the limit of experimental error).

The results show that there is no concentration effect and that the moments of both are nearly the same (1.10) as expected. The small moment is in harmony with a symmetrical structure of barbitone.

Acetanilide, Phenacetin, Acetylsalicylic Acid

There is no previous work on the dipole moment of antipyretics. The author has investigated the dielectric constant and dipole moment of acetanilide, $C_6H_5NHCOCH_3$, in dioxane and benzene, of phenacetin $C_2H_5OC_6H_4NHCOCH_3$ in pure molten state as well as in dioxane solution and of acetylsalicylic acid, $C_6H_4(COOH)OCOCH_3$, in dioxane solution. The dipole moments are calculated by applying the new relationship. The results are shown in Table IV.

The high moment of acetanilide is obviously due to NH group which has a high ionic character (78%). The acetyl group gives a positive component to NH bond when calculated along the connecting links and *vice versa*. The moment along $C=O$, the most polarisable group, comes to 3.4 as compared to 3.6 observed (average value from the data on benzene and dioxane).

The moment of phenacetin is abnormally high and may be due to resonance.

The comparatively low moment of acetylsalicylic acid indicates internal hydrogen bonding.

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